

Catalytic Formation of Methane from Carbon Monoxide and Hydrogen, Part III. A Study of Various Catalysts.

BY KSHITINDRAMOHAN CHAKRABARTY AND
JNANENDRA CHANDRA GHOSH

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 157) an attempt was made to prepare a catalyst which would transform blue water gas, in which hydrogen and carbon monoxide are present in almost equimolecular quantities, to a fuel gas where the percentage of carbon monoxide will be smaller than 20 and that of methane will be larger than 80. A reference to Table IV in that paper will show that at 406°, with nickel-pumice-sugar, carbon-vanadic oxide catalyst, the effluent gases satisfy this condition. The space velocity is rather low being only 5.7 c.c. of gas per minute per c.c. of catalyst space. In this paper will be described an account of a series of experiments carried out with the object of preparing a catalyst which will possess very much higher efficiency and will be at the same time steady.

In these investigations the quantity of catalyst taken in the reaction tube was very much smaller (only 6 g.) than in previous cases so as to make the fall in the activity of the catalyst easily detectable. The same apparatus as was described in the first part (*loc. cit.*, p. 150) was used during these experiments. Reference to Table IV in Part II of these series will show that when the temperature of reaction was near 400°, the percentage of carbon dioxide present in the resulting gases, when an anhydrous mixture of carbon monoxide and hydrogen in the ratio of 1:1 was passed over the catalyst, was almost the same as that of methane. In the experiments recorded in this paper, only carbon dioxide in the resulting gases was estimated, and the percentage of methane formed was considered to be approximately the same as that of carbon dioxide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the catalysts described below asbestos fibre was the supporting material common to all.

Catalyst I.—*Nickel Hydroxide.*

A solution containing 1 gm. of nickel nitrate was added to 1 gm. of asbestos fibre so as to give a semi-solid mass. This mass was next treated with a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide, washed alkali free and dried. During washing nickel hydroxide not deposited directly on this fibre was mostly removed.

Catalyst II (A).—*Nickel Hydroxide and Manganese Hydroxide.*

A solution containing 1 gm. of nickel nitrate and 1 gm. of manganese nitrate was added to 1 gm. of asbestos fibre and treated as in the previous case.

Catalyst II (B).—*Nickel Hydroxide on Manganese Hydroxide.*

In this case manganese hydroxide was first deposited on asbestos fibre in the usual way and next nickel hydroxide was deposited on the product.

Catalyst II (C).—*Manganese Dioxide on Nickel Hydroxide.*

In this case deposition of manganese hydroxide followed that of nickel hydroxide.

Catalyst III (A).—*Nickel Hydroxide and Magnesium Hydroxide.*Catalyst III (B).—*Nickel Hydroxide on Magnesium Hydroxide.*Catalyst III (C).—*Magnesium Hydroxide on Nickel Hydroxide.*Catalyst IV (A).—*Nickel Hydroxide and Zinc Hydroxide.*Catalyst IV (B).—*Nickel Hydroxide on Zinc Hydroxide.*Catalyst V (A).—*Nickel Hydroxide and Lead Hydroxide.*Catalyst VI.—*Ammonium Vanadate on Nickel Hydroxide.*

Nickel Hydroxide was deposited on 1 gm. of asbestos fibre in the usual way. To the product a solution of 0.1 gm. of ammonium vanadate was added and the product dried up.

Catalyst VII.—*Chromium Acetate on Nickel Hydroxide.*

A solution containing 0.6 gm. of chromium acetate was added. Procedure was same as in the previous case.

Catalyst VIII.—*Ammonium Molybdate on Nickel Hydroxide.*

A solution containing 0.6 gm. of ammonium molybdate was taken. Procedure was same as in the previous case.

Catalyst IX (A).—*Nickel Hydroxide and Aluminium Hydroxide.*Catalyst IX (B).—*Nickel Hydroxide on Aluminium Hydroxide.*Catalyst IX (C).—*Aluminium Hydroxide on Nickel Hydroxide.*Catalyst IX (D).—*Nickel Nitrate on Aluminium Hydroxide.*

A solution containing 0.6 gm. of nickel nitrate was added to asbestos fibre upon which aluminium hydroxide was deposited.

In Table I are recorded the results of experiments carried out with the catalysts described above. The temperature of the catalyst before the reacting gases were passed over it, corresponded with that of the furnace and was 800° approximately. On passing the gas mixture at a constant rate, the temperature of catalysts mass rises rapidly as the reaction on its surface is an exothermal one. The temperature of the catalyst soon attains a maximum which is always higher than that of the furnace. The rate at which the temperature rises is a rough measure of catalytic power and the time during which the catalyst retained its maximum temperature indicates the duration of steady activity. The observation was corroborated by analysis of the effluent gases. It was also noticed that the rate of rise of temperature of the catalyst for a constant velocity of the gaseous mixture varied generally in an inverse ratio with the steadiness of the catalyst. It is well known that "excessive activity of catalyst is associated with maximum alterability" and our observation in the present case agrees with that view.

TABLE I,

Catalyst.	Rate in c.c. per min.	Temp. °C	% of CO ₂ .	Remarks.
I ...	58	323	2	On starting the gas mixtures at the rate of 58 c.c. per min. temp. of the catalyst rose from 800° to 323° and was not steady.
II (A) ...	62	370	87	On starting the gas mixture at the rate of 62-66 c.c. per min. temp. rose from 810° to 370°. Within half an hour it lost much of its activity.
II (B)	59	323-25	11.2	On starting the gas mixture at the rate of 59-62 c.c. per min. temp. of the catalyst rose from 806° to 323°. Within 15 mins. the temp. again fell to 310°.
II (C)	66	373-74 (approx.)	80	On starting the gas mixture at the rate 66 c.c. per min. temp. rose from 806° to 375° (approx.), remained steady for 8-5 mins. and was followed by a rapid fall.

Catalyst.	Rate in c.c. per min.	Temp. °C	% of CO ₂ .	Remarks.
III (A) ...	67	382	6	On starting the gas mixture at the rate of 67 c.c. per min. temp. rose from 305° to 382° and was followed by a rapid fall.
III (B) ...	67	355	31.5	On starting the gas mixture at the rate of 67 c.c. per min. temp. rose from 305° to 355°; fell back to 340° in about half an hour.
III (C) ...	62	310	1.8	Temp. rose from 308° to 310° only; rate of passing gas being 62 c.c. per min.
IV (A) ...	...	...	...	No rise of temp. could be seen on passing the gas mixture.
IV (B) ...	...	...	...	No rise of temp. could be seen on passing the gas mixture.
V ...	...	...	...	No rise of temp. could be seen on passing the gas mixture.
VI ...	...	...	...	No rise of temp. could be seen on passing the gas mixture.
VII ...	...	...	...	Slightly active.
VIII ...	...	...	...	On passing the gas mixture at the rate of 64 c.c. per min. temp. rose from 300° to 311° only.
IX (A) ...	57	345-48	36	On starting the gas mixture at the rate of 57 c.c. per min. temp. rose slowly from 300° to 352°. The activity remained steady for about an hour and 45 mins.
IX (B) ...	61	350-51	36	On starting the gas mixture at the rate of 60 c.c. per min. temp. rose slowly from 300° to 350°. The activity remained steady for about 6 hours.
IX (C) ...	62	350	33	On starting the gas mixture at the rate of 65-60 c.c. per min. temp. rose slowly from 305° to 355°. The activity remained steady for about 5 hours.
IX (D) ...	65	355-57	40	On starting the gas mixture at the rate of 63 c.c. per min. temp. rose a bit rapidly from 305° to 362°. Activity was steady for about an hour. On removal of the catalyst from the reaction tube some of the particles showed pyrophoric properties.

From the preceding table it is clear that though some of the catalysts were very active even at the moderately high initial temperature (300°), they were never indefinitely steady. The catalysts associated with aluminium hydroxide however seemed to be promising. The rate of fall of activity was rapid in all the cases. The inactivity of the catalyst in which ammonium vanadate was used seems to be anomalous on the face of the fact that in the previous paper it was seen that vanadium oxide in presence of sugar carbon promoted the reaction. Zinc oxide associated with rare earth has been found by several investigators to catalyse the synthesis of methanol from carbon monoxide and hydrogen. The reaction, $2\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2 = \text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2$, may be considered to be made up of the two reactions,

Medsforth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1452) suggested the following mechanism for the reaction: $\text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2 = \text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$;

$\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2 \longrightarrow \text{H}_2\text{COH} \longrightarrow \text{:CH}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{:CH}_2 + \text{H}_2 \longrightarrow \text{CH}_4$
Methanol being an intermediate product it was hoped that zinc oxide might help the reaction in question. It was not however realized.

An attempt was next made to see how far the activity of the pumice-sugar carbon-nickel catalyst could be increased by increasing the concentration of nickel in the catalyst and also to see whether the catalyst in that case would retain a steady activity.

Preparation of the Catalyst.

Always 10 g. of pumice stone (mixture of powder 2 small pieces) were taken with 2 g. of sugar. The volume of nickel nitrate solution added varied from catalyst to catalyst. Nickel nitrate solution used contained 0.0217 gm. of nickel per c.c. of the solution. Ammonium carbonate was used for preparing the first two catalysts ; the procedure of preparation was practically the same as was described in part II of the series. After each day's work the catalyst was allowed to cool in a slow current of hydrogen. The quantity of catalyst taken inside the reaction tube was always 2 g.

TABLE II.

Catalyst prepared with varying quantities of nickel nitrate solution.	Rate in c.c. per min.	Temp. °C	% of CO ₂	Remarks.
I 20 c.c. sample ...	49	410	17.5	On passing the gas mixture at a rate of 49 c.c. per min. temp. of the catalyst rose slowly from 395° to 410°.
II 30 c.c. sample	56	427	38	On passing the gas mixture at the rate of 56 c.c. per min. temp. of the catalyst slowly rose from 390° to 430°.
III 50 c.c. sample	61	427	40	On passing the gas mixture at the rate of 61 c.c. per min. temp. of the catalyst rose slowly from 390° to 430°.
IV 60 c.c. sample	62	428	39	On passing the gas mixture at the rate of 62 c.c. per min. temp. of the catalyst rose slowly from 395° to 430°.
V 80 c.c. sample ...	76	432	40	On passing the gas mixture at the rate of 75-80 c.c. per min. temp. of the catalyst rose from 395° to 440°.

It will be seen from Table II that the activity of the 30 c.c. sample is much greater than the 20 c.c. one. In the case of catalysts with higher concentration of nickel, the rise of activity was not marked. The rate of loss of activity in these catalysts was slow enough to escape quick detection. But slight deposit of carbon could always be seen in the catalysts on removal from the reaction tube.

From the study of the pumice-sugar charcoal-nickel catalyst it is evident that the rate of fall of activity is very slow as opposed to the behaviour of non-sugar-charcoal catalysts described in this paper. It should be noted however that our attempt to obtain a catalyst of very high and steady efficiency at 400° has not been completely successful. In a forthcoming paper will be described the result obtained by using a mixture of water vapour, carbon monoxide and hydrogen as reactants.